

SHAPE Project NIER: Deep Learning for Video and Time Series Analysis

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Abstract

In the present study we evaluated the possibility of automatically identifying the level of attention / inattention of a car driver, using deep learning techniques to classify the images recorded by a specific equipment able to monitor the driver's gaze. An Eye Tracking system returned videos representing the scene seen by the drivers with a superimposed red cross corresponding to their gaze. The images were labelled by road safety experts in 5 classes, depending on the objects looked at (car, street, rear mirror, background, car interior). We developed a Convolutional Neural Network model (CNN) that was trained and tested on the images to detect the five classes. Specific video pre-processing was necessary. Analyses were performed with OpenCV software library, Keras and Python. The parallelisation of the code was investigated as a proof of concept (PoC) to evaluate a good performance of the computation when moving from this pilot study (that included only three videos) to the use "in production". The code parallelisation was performed on the pre-processing and on the CNN code. In the first case both a multi-thread and a multi-task strategy were tested for the code parallelisation with the latter more performant in small sets of frames case. As for the CNN, we tested a multi-task implementation, using Horovod (4 GPU), and a multi-thread strategy using the mirrored strategy of Tensorflow (2 GPU). Even if a larger database is necessary for further evaluation, the Horovod parallelisation strategy is recommended at this stage. The CNN performance is promising, since, depending on the different combinations of training and testing set, accuracy was always larger than 70%, frequently over 80%. For the specific application this is a really appropriate results. Further studies are necessary to increase the dataset, to tune the models and to finalise the PoC, towards a ready-to-use application.

Introduction

The present report describes the activities and main results of the project "*Deep Learning for Video and Time Series Analysis*".

The aim of the project was to test a Deep Neural Network model, to classify human tasks based on an eye tracking measurement system during a session of driving on public roads to quantify the driver's attention level in different situations.

Anyway, fast processing of this large amount of data is challenging: image analysis is data intensive and highly compute-intensive mostly because of the volume of data. Hence, we propose a parallel computing paradigm (e.g. data parallelism), which would benefit of a computationally efficient hardware such as HPC.

The Deep Neural Network model will be estimated using videos acquired during studies of DICAM - research group on road safety at University of Bologna[†].

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[†] A special thanks to Prof Valeria Vignali and Eng. Ennia Acerra for their contribution and guidance during the project

Data and Deep Neural Network

Experimental sessions

The experiments were conducted by the University of Bologna, DICAM in the context of research activities on the road safety. The experiments included a specific equipment on the driver to monitor their eye movement and estimate the gaze point on the scene. In particular, it consisted in a mobile eye tracking (ASL Mobile Eye Tracking XG) - (Figure 1). The system consists of two digital high resolution camera, one that records the scene image and the other the participant's eye (the movement of the eye's pupil, Figure 2). The images are integrated on a single video recording representing the scene with a superimposed gaze cursor (Figure 3). The participant is able to move freely within the environment wearing small processing device.

Figure 1: ASL Mobile Eye Tracking XG

Figure 2: Detection of eye pupil position

Figure 3: Spatial and temporal synchronisation of the gaze position with respect to the driver visual as detected by the front camera of the eye tracker. The red cross represents the point the driver is looking at.

The experiments output resulted in a video as represented in Figure 3, that needs to be processed according to the specific aim of the study. In particular, as for the data we used in the present study the focus was on the attention level of the driver, to evaluate the possible distracting effect of adaptive cruise control system and car interactive dashboard.

The driver was asked to drive on a freeway, roundtrip, for a total of approximately 20 km, each video of about 20 minutes (including preparation and freeway approaching, later excluded from the analysis). Data were acquired at 30 Hz. Further details on the experiments can be found in [1].

Video Frames classification

Each video was processed manually, frame by frame, by a road safety expert[‡] and each frame was classified according to the classes listed below in Table 1 [2], depending on the object the driver was staring at. According to the classification, the status Attention / Inattention was given. As a result of this activity, all video frames (with the exclusion of the transition phases such as preparation and freeway approaching...) were characterized by a label that, with few changes, were defined as the gold standard for the neural network classifiers, against which accuracy of the classifier were computed.

For the purpose of this study, i.e. evaluating the application of neural networks, the classes were further grouped as represented in Table 1.

Table 1: Frames classification: Class: label as defined by road expert; Assessment: driver's attention or inattention depending on the class; NN classes: gold standard label for the neural network models

Class	Assessment (Attention/Inattention)	Neural Network classes
CAR DASHBOARD	Inattention	[1] CAR INTERIOR
CAR INTERIOR	Inattention	
CAR AHEAD	Attention	[2] CAR
CAR – generic	Attention	
BACKGROUND	Inattention	[3] BACKGROUND (sfondo)
Side view mirror	Attention	[4] SIDE VIEW MIRROR (specchietti)
ROAD	Attention	[5] ROAD (strada)
Rear view mirror	Attention	*
STREET SIGN	Attention	*

*not considered for neural network classification because of very few occurrences

Pre processing

In the present study we evaluated three videos to classify frames using a CNN, as described later. The labelling of the frames was set according to the Table 1 from above.

The three different videos correspond to three different drivers and driving sessions.

Each video was preprocessed eliminating the transitional phases at the beginning and end of the experimental sessions.

Hence, each video (V_i) resulted in N frames and M minutes of driving in the conditions described in the previous section.

The experiment consisted in a back and forth trip on the freeway near the city. In the present study only one way is considered to avoid intra-video differences in terms of light exposure in the video.

Table 2: Description of the videos analysed

	N frames	Duration	Note
V1	6363	212 s	
V2	7674	256 s	
V3	6835	228 s	Many frames had to be canceled due to bad recording. final

[‡] Researcher on road safety, DICAM - University of Bologna

30 frames /sec

In addition, a specific cropping function was implemented in order to obtain an 80x80 pixels size frame with the red cross centered in it. Such size was empirically selected as the most suitable for the specific purpose. after the evaluation of other sizes (e.g. 120 x120 pixels)

In addition, since the video format was available in a compressed format, the red lines used to identified the object of interest, had to be detected using a range of values (threshold) on the bitmap RGB values.

The OpenCV library (and its Python interfaces) was used for video processing [3]. In addition, both three channel videos (RGB) and 1 channel video (grey scale) were considered for further analyses.

Models definition and evaluation

Training and Testing

Each frame of each video was labelled by an expert, according to the five classes. Then each video was divided into a training and testing sets. The training set corresponds to the first 80% frames of each video, while the testing set to the remaining 20% frames ($V_{i_{TR}}$ $V_{i_{TE}}$).

Models

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) [4] were used to recognise the different classes for each frame in an automatic way.

We developed our CNN according to the literature and empirical experiments on some images. In particular CNN are typically used for images, with outstanding results, due to their ability to detect spatial correlations [5][6]. Other options were taken into consideration, such as already pre-trained CNN able to detect objects with only final layer training (e.g. YOLO, [7]), but their implementation in this case was not pursued because the superimposed “viewfinder” interfered with the object identification.

The model is described in the scheme below (Figure 4) and consisted of a conv2D network to evaluate images, following by max_pooling and dropout [8]. The following layer was a mono-dimensional convolution and later a dense layer. The output layer consisted of five neurons each corresponding to one of the five classes. For a given class, each neuron returns a probability value from (0-1), of belonging to the specific class.

Figure 4: Scheme of the structure of the CNN used in the study

The model used by NIER for the image classification analysis has been developed using the Keras implementation provided by Tensorflow [9],[10],[11].

Data analysis and accuracy

The models were estimated considering different combinations of training sets and the accuracy estimated with different combinations of test sets, along the three videos. This procedure was carried out to evaluate the dependency of results on the specific videos, and on the data numerosity. In addition, we aimed at estimating the accuracy of a model trained on one or more video(s), testing it on a different video.

The data set combinations are represented in Figure 5. It represents the data that were used to estimate the model (training set) and the data that were used to compute accuracy of the models (testing set).

We evaluated three different models, considering different hyperparameters (filters of dimension 32/64) and considering RGB (three channels) or gray scale (single channel) videos.

In any case, for each video the training set (80%) and testing set (20%) were kept segregated (i.e. training set was always used only for training, testing set only for testing)

Figure 5: Training and testing set combinations data from different videos: **a)** models are trained and tested using data from the same video; **b)** models are trained using the combination of two videos and tested on the third one; **c)** the model is trained on the three videos combined and tested on a single one. Testing and training data were kept segregated.

In particular, this procedure was parallelised, together with the video processing, and methods and results are presented in the following section.

Parallelization of the code

CINECA contribution to this SHAPE project has been related to the parallelisation of the code used by NIER. This code is used to perform image classification analysis on images extracted from a video.

The python code provided by NIER can be seen as made of two main blocks. This distinction can be performed since these two blocks can be executed separately and have different goals, namely:

- Pre-processing: a first analysis step on the video to be examined. The video frames are extracted, cropped and resized before being saved as single pictures.
- Image classification: here the deep learning model is trained and tested to perform the image analysis step. The input data consists of the set of figures previously extracted and modified from the frames of the video, together with a second set of figures that have been manually classified.

Two different parallelisation strategies have been tested for both the pre-processing and image classification codes, as explained in the following sections.

Pre-processing

The source video used for the pre-processing step consists of 108000 frames. Inside the code, the frames are individually extracted from the video, cropped and stored on disk. This type of workflow allows to realise a simple

parallelisation of the code, by distributing the workload among several workers. The simplicity depends on the fact that each worker can deal with a specific set of frames, without any type of interaction with the other workers. The cropping algorithm is not described here since parallelisation does not occur inside of it. It can be considered as a function that is applied to each frame and each worker takes care of this function execution on its own set of frames.

The preprocessing code can be summarised with three main actions:

1. Opening of the video file
2. Execution of `get_frames()` function
3. Execution of `crop_frames()` function

The `get_frames()` function is used to extract the frames from the video and to save them, without any processing, as individual images on file. The `crop_frames()` function is used to load the individually stored frames, crop them and save them as new images.

From a preliminary profiling analysis, performed on the provided NIER code at its initial state using python cProfile module [12], it has been found that the parallelisation of both `get_frames` (62% of time to solution) and `crop_frames` (37 % of time to solution) was needed to improve the performances of the pre-processing code.

Two different strategies, namely a multi-thread and a multi-task strategy, have been tested for the code parallelization. For the multi-thread strategy the multi-processing python module has been used [13], while for the multi-task strategy the `mpi4py` python module was used [14]. The differences between the two approaches can be seen below (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Differences between the multi-task and the multi-thread parallelization strategies

With the multi-task (MPI) strategy, for an execution with N workers (tasks), N different executions of the code are performed, so inside each execution the video is opened, a subset of frames is extracted and stored, and a subset of the output frames are read, cropped and saved. Among all the available frames, each task processes a range of frames, based on the value of the task rank.

The multi-thread strategy uses a fork-join mechanism with threads. The code is executed on a single task and multiple threads are used to distribute the workload only on selected blocks of code, where most of the execution time is spent. In the present case, these blocks are represented by the `extract_frames()` and `crop_frames()` functions. Multiple threads are used on these functions so that each thread deals with the extraction-storing and reading-cropping-storing of a specific subset of frames.

The two different approaches have been tested in the processing of three different sets of frames, namely a total amount of 1000, 10000 and 100000 frames. The obtained results are reported in Figure 7 and have been obtained by running the code on Galileo cluster.

Figure 7: Comparison of the performances obtained with the two different parallelisation strategies for the pre-processing code.

The results are reported in terms of speed-up and are separately shown for the `extract_frames` and `crop_frames` functions, but also for the total execution of the code. Each row of Figure 7 represents the results obtained for a subset of frames (from top to bottom: 1000, 10000, 100000). The reported results are relative to the speed-up value obtained by running the code with 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32 and 36 (full node) threads-tasks, where the speed-up value is calculated as

$$SU_n = (\text{execution time with 1 worker}) / (\text{execution time with } n \text{ workers})$$

With small sets of frames (1000 and 10000), the multi-task strategy allows to obtain better performances with respect to the multi-thread strategy. Moreover, since the multi-thread strategy is a form of shared memory parallelisation, its limit is represented by the number of cores that are present on the computing node (36 for the case of Galileo cluster). With the multi-threaded approach, the best SU is achieved by leaving some cores free for OS threads management. When pre-processing of a video with a much higher number of frames, a multi-node parallelisation could be needed to obtain a sensible speed-up of the tasks. In this case only the multi-task strategy could be used, so this is the suggested strategy to be used in the future.

CNN model

The model used by NIER for the image classification analysis has been developed using the Keras implementation provided by Tensorflow [9],[10]. When dealing with the parallelisation of a deep learning model, two different strategies are available: data or model parallelisation [15]. The data parallelisation is used when a great amount of data is processed by the model. In this case the data is shared among the workers and the model, with all its components, is executed on each worker. In order to obtain a unique model, several synchronisation steps are required to share the weight values computed by each worker. In fact, as each worker deals with a subset of all the data, a different set of weights is computed by each worker. The model parallelisation strategy deals with a distribution of the model blocks among the workers. In this case the output of a worker is used as input by another worker, depending on how the model components are distributed.

The two different strategies that have been tested in the present project are both based on data parallelism. As for the case of the pre-processing code, we tested a multi-task implementation, using Horovod [16], and a multi-thread strategy using the mirrored strategy implemented in Tensorflow [17]. The main differences are related to the fact that Horovod parallelism is based on MPI, so a parallelisation using N workers imply an execution of the code on

N devices, CPUs and GPUs (where available). The parallelisation using the mirrored strategy function is used to distribute particularly demanding tasks (the model creation and training steps) among several workers-devices, starting from a main thread execution. The limit of the mirrored strategy parallelisation is related to the fact that the maximum number of usable workers is equal to the number of the devices available on the computing node, while the parallelisation with Horovod allows to perform a multi-node parallelisation.

The model parallelisation strategies have been tested on the GPU partition of Galileo cluster, a set of computing nodes with 2 K80 nVidia GPUs per node. For the mirror distributed strategy a maximum value of 2 GPUs has been used, while for the Horovod parallelisation we tested also the case with 4 GPUs on two nodes. From the software point of view, we used Tensorflow v2.0.0 and Horovod v0.18.2.

The database of classified images is rather small (approximately 3100 images with a resolution of 80x80 pixels), so for a proper scalability test a bigger database would be needed to better exploit the GPUs computational power.

Figure 8: Comparison of epoch loss and accuracy values obtained for the case of parallelisation using mirrored strategy. The values are plotted against the wall time.

Figure 9: comparison of epoch loss and accuracy values obtained for the case of parallelisation using Horovod. The values are plotted against the wall time.

The obtained results are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9 for the cases of parallelisation with mirrored strategy and Horovod, respectively. The results are plotted against the wall time in order to show the speed-up gained with the parallel execution. In all the cases 200 training epochs have been run. For this particular test, the mirrored strategy shows a better scaling with respect to the Horovod implementation: starting with a comparable wall time for the 1 GPU case, a 1.66x speed-up has been obtained with the mirrored strategy parallelisation, using 2 GPUs, while a 1.29x speed-up has been obtained using Horovod.

We remark that for a proper scaling test a bigger database should be used. In any case, our suggestion would be to use Horovod as a parallelisation strategy, in order to have a more flexible environment, in terms of number of GPUs and computing nodes used for the model training.

Results of the classification and further developments

Results showed we did not find particular difference between the three kinds of models. Hence below figures considering Grey scale video and 64-32 filters CNN are represented.

Figure 10: Accuracy of the models (Grayscale video) trained combining videos V1 and V2 as training set and using V2 as test set (left panel). Accuracy of the models trained and tested on the same video (right panel)

The results from Figure 10 showed that a large percentage of data is correctly classified. In addition, further analyses showed that the misclassified classes were possibly in the same attention / inattention assessment, hence not causing big impact in the specific application.

Further studies should be carried out to better quantify this aspect. In addition, other convolutional networks (already trained) could be used, and modified. Furthermore, we intend to use also the position of the scene of interest within the view scene, that has not been used so far.

However, the pilot study and the results on the parallelisation of the code allow promising evaluation on performing these analyses automatically on several videos.

References

- [1] Acerra et al, “EEG-Based Mental Workload and Perception-Reaction Time of the Drivers While Using Adaptive Cruise Control In book: Human Mental Workload: Models and Applications, Third International Symposium, H-WORKLOAD 2019 Rome, Italy, November 14–15, 2019 Proceedings, pp226-239
- [2] Di Flumeri G. et al. EEG-Based Mental Workload Neurometric to Evaluate the Impact of Different Traffic and Road Conditions in Real Driving Settings Front. Hum. Neurosci 2018 Dec 18;12:509
- [3] <https://opencv.org/>
- [4] <https://towardsdatascience.com/a-comprehensive-guide-to-convolutional-neural-networks-the-eli5-way-3bd2b1164a53>
- [5] A.Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, G. E. Hinton. “ImageNet classification with deep convolutional neural networks”, Communications of the ACM Volume 60, Issue 6 June 2017 pag 5-ff
- [6] F.E. Curtis,K. Scheinberg: “Optimization Methods for Supervised Machine Learning” in Tutorials in Operations Research, 2017 INFORMS, pp. 89-114
- [7] J. Redmon*, S. Divvala, R. G., A. Farhadi “You Only Look Once:Unified, Real-Time Object Detection arXiv:1506.02640v5 [cs.CV] 9 May 2016, <http://pjreddie.com/yolo/>
- [8] A.Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, G. E. Hinton. “ImageNet classification with deep convolutional neural networks”, Communications of the ACM Volume 60, Issue 6 June 2017 pag 5-ff
- [9] <https://keras.io/>
- [10]<https://www.tensorflow.org/>
- [11]A. Gulli, A. Kapoor, S. Pal “Deep Learning with TensorFlow 2 and Keras” (Second Edition, Dec.2019) Regression, ConvNets, GANs, RNNs, NLP, and more with TensorFlow 2 and the Keras API. Ed. PACKT Birmingham – Mumbai
- [12]<https://docs.python.org/3/library/profile.html>
- [13]<https://docs.python.org/3/library/multiprocessing.html>
- [14]<https://mpi4py.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>
- [15]M. Madijagan, S. Sridhar Raj, “Chapter 1 - Parallel Computing, Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) and New Hardware for Deep Learning in Computational Intelligence Research”, Editor(s): Arun Kumar Sangaiah, Deep Learning and Parallel Computing Environment for Bioengineering Systems, Academic Press, 2019, Pages 1-15
- [16]<https://github.com/horovod/horovod>
- [17]https://www.tensorflow.org/api_docs/python/tf/distribute/MirroredStrategy

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE project funded in part by the EU’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (2014-2020) under grant agreement 823767.